
Bridging the Gender Gap: Women Empowerment Index Across Indian States

Shriya Sethi¹ and Ashutosh Priya²

¹ Research Scholar, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly

² Professor, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly

Abstract

Women Empowerment is a crucial concept of a developing economy like India. Empowering women is a step towards empowering the nation. It not only enhances education, health and economic stability but works towards a more inclusive society. It helps break traditional barriers and enables women to contribute fully to national development.

This research paper explores the multifaceted dimensions of women empowerment in all the states of India, a critical issue in the nation's socio-economic development. The study investigates the progress, challenges, and opportunities in empowering women across economic, cultural political and social dimensions. The paper uses secondary data from several Government reports to calculate Women Empowerment Index (WEI) by examining variations in literacy rates, Institutional delivery patterns, political representation and Women work force ratio. Further, it creates a comparison among all the states from Best to Worst in WEI. In conclusion, this research will contribute valuable insight by addressing various barriers and opportunities so that women can unlock their potential, drive progress and creating a more inclusive and equitable world for future generations.

Historical Background

The history of women empowerment in India passes through a rich yet complex structure shaped by social, cultural, and political changes in it. Following is a broad overview of progressive reform and persistent challenges.

Ancient and Medieval Periods

In the early Vedic times, Women had significant roles to play with some of the women even holding positions of authority. They even participated in philosophical debates and were authors of hymns. The Medieval Period saw severe fluctuation in the position of women due to the increasing restrictions and diminished status. Several women were engaged in religious and social reform because societal norms limited their roles and opportunities compared to earlier periods. Later the Bhakti movement, which began in the 7th century, included several female saints like Mirabai, who challenged social norms.

Colonial Era (19th - Early 20th Century)

During British rule, social reformers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, and Jyotirao Phule advocated for women's education, and the abolition of practices like Sati and child marriage. These efforts led to legal changes and greater access to education. Further, the efforts made by Savitribai Phule and her husband Jyotirao Phule played a crucial role in advancing women's education. Also, the establishment of Bethune School in Kolkata for girls was another development. All this led to increased opportunities, yet access was limited and uneven. The existence of traditional practices and restrictions created hindrances in the way of women's empowerment.

Independence Movement (Early to Mid-20th Century)

Women played a crucial role in the Indian independence movement. Sarojini Naidu, Kasturba Gandhi and Usha Mehta were involved in various capacities, from political activism to leadership roles. In 1950 the Indian Constitution adopted equal rights to women and prohibited discrimination based on sex.

Post-Independence (Late 20th Century to Present)

Dowry Prohibition Act (1961), the Equal Remuneration Act (1976), and the Protection of Human Rights Act (1993) were introduced to safeguard the interests of women. Also, the introduction of the Domestic Violence Act (2005) aimed to address violence against women. The 1970s and 80s saw the rise of women's movements such as the All-India Democratic Women's Association (AIDWA). Its first campaign focused on issues related to Dowry and even fought for victims' justice. All this marked a period of active advocacy. Further, the 1990s and 2000s saw increased participation of women in politics, including the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments, which reserved seats for women in local self-governance.

Recent Developments

The global #MeToo movement gained action in India by bringing the issues of sexual harassment and violence against women to the forefront of public discourse. More recent legal changes include amendments to laws related to sexual offenses, such as the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013, in response to high-profile cases of sexual violence.

Throughout history, Indian women have shown resilience and leadership, contributing significantly to the nation's progress. Despite this, challenges such as gender-based violence, discrimination, and economic disparity remain, necessitating ongoing efforts toward true gender equality.

Indicators for the Measurement of Women Empowerment Index

1. Literacy Rates

Globally, 129 million girls are out of school with 32 million at the primary level, 30 million at the lower-secondary level and 67 million at the upper-secondary level. These figures underscore the critical issue of educational exclusion due to numerous barriers. In India, the situation is extremely critical with 23 million girls dropping out of school annually once they begin menstruation. All this is largely due to insufficient sanitary facilities and inadequate hygiene forcing girls to leave school prematurely, severely affecting their educational prospects.

Although India's literacy rate has improved from 73% in 2011 to 77.7% in 2022 yet it's below the global average of 86.5. The male literacy rate stands at 84.7%, while the female literacy rate lags at 70.3%, representing gender disparity. Several factors contribute to this gender gap, including gender-based discrimination, cultural norms that prioritize boys' education, and inadequate school infrastructure. Social expectations often confine girls to household roles, undermining their educational opportunities, and poor facilities. Among all the states Kerala.

Kerala tops the list of the highest literacy rate of 96.2% and Andhra Pradesh and Rajasthan at the lowest with 66.4% and 69.7% respectively. Also, the urban-rural divide is stark with rural literacy at 73.5% compared to 87.7% in urban areas.

In Figure 1 Kerala (95.2%) leads in female literacy, followed by Mizoram (89.4%) and Delhi (82.4%) reflecting strong educational infrastructure and progressive attitude. Goa (81.84%) and Tripura (83.15%) also show commendable female literacy rates. In contrast, Rajasthan (57.6%), Andhra Pradesh at 59.5% and Bihar (60.5%) represent significant gender disparities and socio-economic challenges. Uttar Pradesh (63.4%) also indicates a need for focused educational policies.

2. Institutional Delivery

Institutional birth refers to the availability of amenities during the delivery of a baby in a hospital or a clinic rather than at home. Current Statistics show that about 88% of births occur in institutions. Major contribution is largely attributed to government health initiatives and improved healthcare infrastructure. Several government program such as the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY), provides financial incentives to pregnant women who deliver in health institutions. The National Health Mission (NHM) also supports maternal and child health services. These initiatives have severely pampered higher institutional birth rates and infant health. Delivering in a medical facility provides various health benefits, it not only provides access to trained healthcare professionals but also a few essential services, which can significantly reduce maternal and infant mortality rates and ease out all the complications during the whole process. Another major advantage of Institutional deliveries is the postnatal care for both the mother and the newborn, including vaccinations and early detection of health issues. Even after all these various challenges such as access to quality health care, lack of sufficient infrastructure, proper sanitation, transportation issues and lack of awareness can hinder access to institutional births.

Figure 2 shows that states on the right of the graph (Kerala, Goa, Tamil Nadu, Telangana, and Karnataka) have very high institutional birth rates. In contrast, the states on the left (Nagaland, Meghalaya, Jharkhand, Bihar, and Arunachal Pradesh) have lower institutional birth rates indicating a larger proportion of births in these states still occur outside of medical institutions may be at home or with traditional birth attendants.

3. Political Representation of Women in India

Just like other indicators political representation of women has seen progress but is mixed with unending challenges. Sarojini Naidu and Indira Gandhi have been involved politically breaking all the stereotypes. However, systemic representation has been slower to evolve. In 1950, the Indian Constitution granted women the right to vote and stand for elections. Another important measure was the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments in 1992 that mandated 33% reservation for women in local government bodies. This led to increased female representation making many women emerge as leaders and decision-makers in their communities. Another most discussed proposal aimed at enhancing women's representation is the Women's Reservation Bill. It was introduced in various forms since 1996. The bill seeks to reserve 33% of seats in the Lok Sabha and state legislative assemblies for women. Despite the support, the bill has faced many delays and political resistance, preventing its enactment. Yet several challenges hinder the way. A few of these are socio-cultural barriers, limited access to resources and political violence. Women often face obstacles in securing nominations and winning elections in many regions especially with patriarchal norms.

Recent trends show a large number of women participating in politics, driven by increased political awareness and support from society. Initiatives such as the Nari Shakti Vandan Adhiniyam 2023 gave 1/3rd reservation to women in Lok Sabha and State Legislature to encourage women to become public representatives.

Figure 3 seems to compare the percentages of political representation across different states/UTs, with some states having no political representation at the lowest level (0%) and others having relatively higher percentages. For example, Mizoram and Nagaland have 0% representation at the lowest level, while Chhattisgarh has the highest at 14.44%.

4. Workforce Participation

India's rapid economic growth highlights its potential to become the third-largest economy by 2030. However, this progress is accompanied by a decline in female workforce participation. The female labor force participation rate has dropped. Despite India's economic advancements our women workforce is lower than Pakistan's workforce.

Years	LFPR (in %)	WPR (in %)
2017-18	23.3	22.0
2018-19	24.5	23.3
2019-20	30.0	28.7
2020-21	32.5	31.4
2021-22	32.8	31.7
2022-23	37.0	35.9

Source: PLFS, MoSPI

The participation of women in the workforce in India has seen a notable increase from 2017-18 to 2022-23. Data from the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) reveals that the Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) for women aged 15 and above rose from 23.3% in 2017- 18 to 37.0% in 2022-23 whereas the Worker Population

Ratio (WPR) increased from 22.0% to 35.9% in the same period. This growth indicates a significant rise

in women's involvement in the labor market.

Despite the progress several factors such as Gender discrimination including job segregation and lower pay for similar kind of work. Unpaid care and domestic work inadequate urban infrastructure, social norms and fears related to safety at the workplace stops women from working. Additionally, the informal sector's prevalence and the lack of decent, accessible jobs for women further exacerbate the issue.

Government's initiatives such as the Aatmanirbhar Bharat package provides fiscal stimulus and supports new employment opportunities. Aatmanirbhar Bharat Rojgar Yojana (ABRY) and the Prime Minister Street Vendor's Atma Nirbhar Nidhi (PM SVANidhi) offer financial help to regenerate employment and support small businesses that were impacted by the COVID-19. Also, Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY) works towards providing collateral-free loans for small businesses whereas the Production Linked Incentive (PLI) scheme aims to create job opportunities and encourage local production. Another scheme such as Make in India and Digital India provides specialized training for women to boost their employability and entrepreneurial skills.

Figure 5 compares the Female Workforce Participation Rate (WPR) percentages in different states of India, highlighting those with the lowest and highest participation rates. Bihar has the lowest rate at 9.4%, while Himachal Pradesh has the highest at 63.1%.

Women Empowerment

Women Empowerment is letting women control their lives, make decisions, and participate fully in society. This concept is the outcome of feminist movements, gender equality advocacy and international organizations. It has been in vogue for a long time but gained popularity in the late 20th century through various international conferences. Also, the term has been limelight in the United Nations and various NGOs that focused on Gender issues. The term "Empowerment" means "to give authority" to the marginalized and disadvantaged group. Empowerment when combined with women refers to enhancing the social, economic and political power of women in the society.

India's history is replete with powerful women leaders such as Rani Lakshmibai of Jhansi, and Sarojini Naidu, who played pivotal roles in the struggle for independence. However, post- independence, the status of women is still a question due to its deep-rooted patriarchal norms, limited access to education, healthcare and a few economic opportunities.

Method to Calculate Women Empowerment Index

This research paper aims to provide a measurement of women empowerment. The indicators have been strategically selected to serve different dimensions of the topic. Female literacy rate as a measure for education empowerment, Worker population ratio as an indicator of economic empowerment, Institutional Delivery is used for health empowerment and Representation of women in political assemblies is used to capture political empowerment.

All the dimensions mentioned above are allotted equal weightage. The variables are represented as

X_1 represents literacy rate

X_2 represents Institutional Deliveries

X_3 represent women in Political assemblies

X_4 represent women's worker population (WPR)

Women Empowerment Index (WEI) for each state is calculated as

$$WEI = 0.25 * X_1 + 0.25 * X_2 + 0.25 * X_3 + 0.25 * X_4$$

State	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	WEI
Sikkim	76.43	58.5	94.7	9.38	59.7525
Himachal Pradesh	80.5	63.1	88.2	5.88	59.42
Kerala	95.2	27.1	99.8	7.86	57.49
Chhattisgarh	68.7	52.1	85.7	14.44	55.235
Tamil Nadu	77.9	38.3	99.6	5.13	55.2325
Maharashtra	78.4	37.7	94.7	8.33	54.7825
Goa	81.84	24.9	99.7	5	52.86
Mizoram	89.4	34.9	85.8	0	52.525
Telangana	65.1	41.8	97	5.04	52.235
Gujarat	74.8	30.7	94.3	7.14	51.735
West Bengal	76.1	23.1	91.7	13.7	51.15
Odisha	70.3	31.8	92.2	8.9	50.8
Madhya Pradesh	65.5	37.2	90.7	9.13	50.6325
Karnataka	70.5	31.7	97	3.14	50.585
Rajasthan	57.6	37.6	94.9	12	50.525
Andhra Pradesh	59.5	37.6	96.5	8	50.4
Uttarakhand	80.7	30.1	83.2	7.14	50.285
Tripura	83.15	23.5	89.2	5	50.2125
Delhi	82.4	14.5	91.8	11.43	50.0325

Punjab	78.5	21.8	94.3	5.13	49.9325
Haryana	71.3	14.7	94.9	10	47.725
Jharkhand	64.7	35.2	75.8	12.35	47.0125
Assam	81.2	14.2	84.1	4.76	46.065
Manipur	73.17	26.8	79.9	3.33	45.8
Meghalaya	73.78	44.1	58.1	5.08	45.265
Uttar Pradesh	63.4	17.2	83.4	10.55	43.6375
Arunachal Pradesh	59.57	20.8	79.2	5	41.1425
Bihar	60.5	9.4	76.2	10.7	39.2
Nagaland	76.69	31.1	45.7	0	38.3725

Conclusion & Finding

The data highlights the disparities in women's empowerment across Indian states and union territories.

Kerala excels with the highest female literacy rate of 95.2% and institutional births of 99.8%, though its female workforce participation rate is only 27.1%. But due to strong literacy and work participation rates, Sikkim and Himachal Pradesh scores highest in the Women Empowerment Index (WEI). Conversely, Bihar and Nagaland have some of the lowest WEI scores, reflecting poor performance in literacy, workforce participation and political representation. The data indicates significant regional differences. States in the northeast and north India generally lag behind in women's empowerment.

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